

Study the Effect of Benzene on Human Body Fat in Basrah, Iraq

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Abstract

Background: Benzene is a frequent industrial and environmental pollutant that can induce hematologic and metabolic problems. **Aim of study:** Determine the impact of benzene exposure on body fat and hematological parameters among petrol station worker in Basrah, Iraq. **Methodology:** A comparative cross-sectional study was conducted among 25 exposed petrol station workers and 25 non-exposed controls. Blood samples were analyzed for lipid profile and hematological parameters using standard biochemical and hematology analyzers. Statistical significance was determined at ($p \leq 0.05$). **Results:** Compared with controls, exposed workers showed significantly lower total cholesterol (153.2 vs. 171.6 mg/dL, $p=0.03$) and HDL (35.8 vs. 47.9 mg/dL, $p=0.02$), while LDL (108.3 vs. 96.4 mg/dL, $p=0.04$) and triglycerides (134.7 vs. 97.5 mg/dL, $p=0.01$) were higher. Workers also had slightly higher RBC, hemoglobin, and WBC counts ($p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** Benzene exposure at work was related with adverse lipid changes and modest hematological abnormalities in petrol station workers. To reduce health hazards, it is suggested use personal protective equipment, increase workplace ventilation, and conduct regular health monitoring.

Introduction

Benzene is an essential industrial ingredient that is widely utilized in the rubber, petrochemical, and interior decoration sectors, among others. Benzene, also referred to as benzol, is a colorless, very flammable liquid. It is found in the soil, water, and air, and it swiftly evaporates into the atmosphere [1]. It comes from both natural and industrial sources, including crude oil, coal tar, and petroleum. Additionally, it is present in gasoline and cigarette smoke [2]. Benzene is also a major environmental contaminant. It may disrupt the hematological system, create clinical signs, and potentially promote aplastic anemia and leukemia [3]. Benzene is a ubiquitous contaminant that mostly accumulates in adipose tissue, which plays an essential role in metabolic disorders. According to the most recent research, benzene exposure has been linked to a variety of metabolic diseases, however the effect on adipose tissue is uncertain [4]. Research indicates that benzene and ethylene oxide are common carcinogens in workplaces and among benzene-exposed personnel. Exposure to benzene at low levels (< 1 ppm) has been linked to non-cancerous abnormalities, including

hematological alterations and nervous system diseases [5].

Benzene is a proven human carcinogen and poses a significant public health risk. After entering the body, primarily by inhalation, benzene is metabolically metabolized by cytochrome P450 enzymes, and its metabolites disperse to lipid-rich tissues (including bone marrow) according to their fat content and rate of blood perfusion, resulting in many severe health consequences [6]. Fats are chemical substances that are either acidic or unsaturated. Glycerides, or fats, are esters of certain fatty acids with glycerol [7].

Because benzene mostly accumulates in fat-rich tissues upon entrance into the human body [8], fat content in the body and in tissues or organs (such as blood and liver) may influence the distribution and/or metabolism of benzene, and hence benzene-induced toxicity. Furthermore, studies have shown that fat content can affect erythroid-related hematologic parameters. In rats fed a fatty-rich diet, the proportion of erythroid precursors in bone marrow cells rose significantly [9]. In a rat model of high-fat diet-induced obesity, erythrocyte dysfunction was created by raising their

More Information

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Benzene, body fat, lipid profile, occupational exposure.

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oxidative stress levels and diminishing their lifespan. Patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease were also more likely to have high red cell distribution width (RDW) and higher hemoglobin (Hb) levels. In addition, indices of blood fat content, such as serum cholesterol (TC) and triglycerides (TG), were linked to hematological disorders [10]. However, few research has studied the impact of fat content on the correlations between benzene exposure and erythroid-related hematologic markers [6]. The current study aims to determine the effect of benzene exposure on body lipids and blood parameters among petrol station workers in Basra, Iraq.

Methodology

Study Population

Two groups were included in the study: a control group of 25 people who had no occupational exposure to fuel stations and an exposed group of 25 workers who worked at three gas stations: the Pearl of Basrah, the Arabian Gulf Station, and the Jubailah Station. Males and females between the ages of 18 and 60 were among the participants. During the data gathering

procedure, it was discovered that a number of workers in the exposed group had pre-existing chronic diseases, including diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and anemia.

Study Duration

The study was conducted over a three-month period

Sample Collection and Laboratory Analysis

Each participant had a venous blood sample taken using Gel tubes (Managa, Spain) for biochemical analysis and EDTA tubes (Managa, Spain) for hematological analysis. To prevent hemolysis and guarantee the correctness of the data, every sample was appropriately labeled and processed right away. The Sysmex XT-1800i automated hematology analyzer was used to evaluate hematological parameters such as complete blood count (CBC). To evaluate any changes caused by benzene exposure, the AL-Monarch Biochemical Analyzer (Biorex Diagnosis, USA) was used to assess the lipid profile and liver enzyme levels. Proper quality control techniques were used throughout the analyses to guarantee the results were reliable and accurate (Table 1).

Table 1. Materials Used in this Study

Subject name	Manufacture company	Country
Alcohol	The general company for petrochemical industries	Iraq
Aspartate Aminotransferase	Roche diagnostice	USA
Blaster	Oansin Blaster	Turkey
Cotton	Better cotton	Basrah- Iraq
Cell pack	Sysmex	Japan
EDTA tube	Managa	Spain
Gell tube	Managa	Spain
Monarch device	Biorex dignosis	USA
Needl	The general commpany for petrochemical industries	Iraq
Syringa	The general company for petrochemical industries	Iraq
Stromatolyser-4DS-(FFS)	Sysmex	Japan
Stromatolyser-4DL-(FFD)	Sysmex	japan
Stromatolyser-FB-(FBA)	Sysmex	japan
Turnka	Ashhab Company	Basrah- Iraq
XT-1800i	Sysmex	japan

Data Analysis

The collected data were statistically examined to compare the outcomes of fuel station employees (exposed group) with non-exposed persons (control group). The effect of benzene exposure on lipid profile and hematological markers was assessed using statistical significance at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

The study involved 25 petrol station workers (exposed group) and 25 non-exposed persons (control group). The biochemical and hematological parameters were compared between the two groups to determine the impact of benzene exposure. The findings revealed substantial differences in lipid profiles and blood

indices between petrol station workers and the control group.

(Figure 1) illustrates the distribution of the study sample according to age group. The majority of workers fall within the (20–29) year age group, followed by the (30–39) year group. A smaller proportion of participants are younger than 20 years or aged 40 years and above. This indicates that most individuals occupationally exposed to benzene belong to the young adult category, reflecting the dominant age group within the active industrial workforce.

Figure 1: Distribution of Study Sample According to Age Group

The control group had a substantially higher mean total cholesterol level (171.6 mg/dL) than the workers (153.2 mg/dL), with a *p*-value of 0.03. HDL (High-Density Lipoprotein, or "Good Cholesterol"): The control group has a substantially higher mean HDL level (47.9 mg/dL) than the workers (35.8 mg/dL), with a *p*-value of 0.02. Lower HDL levels in workers are typically seen as a poor health indication. LDL (Low-Density Lipoprotein, or "bad cholesterol"): The workers had a substantially higher mean LDL level (108.3 mg/dL) than the control group (96.4 mg/dL), with a *p*-value of 0.04. This is a poor health indication for the employees. The workers have a significantly higher mean triglyceride level (134.7 mg/dL) compared to the control group (97.5 mg/dL), with a *p*-value of 0.01, (Table 2).

Table 2. Comparison of Lipid Profile between Petrol Station Workers and Control Group

Parameter	Study population		<i>p</i> -value
	Workers (exposed group) (Mean ± SD)	Control (non-exposed) (Mean ± SD)	
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	153.2 ± 25.4	171.6 ± 22.1	0.03*
HDL (mg/dL)	35.8 ± 8.6	47.9 ± 9.3	0.02*
LDL (mg/dL)	108.3 ± 22.5	96.4 ± 18.9	0.04*
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	134.7 ± 41.2	97.5 ± 30.8	0.01*

Note: *Significant test at 0.05 level, *Abbreviation: **LDL**, low density lipoproteins cholesterol; **HDL**, high density lipoproteins cholesterol

Workers had a slightly higher mean RBC count ($5.52 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$) than the control group ($5.38 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$) (*p*-value = 0.04). Workers have a slightly but substantially higher average hemoglobin level (14.6 g/dL) than the control

group (14.2 g/dL), with a *p*-value of 0.03. Workers had a substantially higher mean WBC count ($8.12 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) than the control group ($7.1 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) (*p*-value = 0.02), Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of Hematological Parameters between Petrol Station Workers and Control Group

Parameter	Study population		<i>p</i> -value
	workers (exposed group) (Mean ± SD)	Control (non-exposed) (Mean ± SD)	
RBC ($\times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$)	5.52 ± 0.48	5.38 ± 0.42	0.04*
HGB (g/dL)	14.6 ± 0.8	14.2 ± 0.7	0.03*
WBC ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	8.12 ± 2.1	7.1 ± 1.6	0.02*

Note: *Significant test at 0.05 level, *Abbreviation: **RBC**, red blood cells; **HGB**, hemoglobin; **WBC**, white blood cells

Discussion

This comparative cross-sectional study evaluated the effect of occupational benzene exposure among petrol station workers in Basrah, Iraq, on lipid profile and hematological parameters. The predominance of benzene-exposed workers in the younger age group observed in this study is consistent with the findings of a cross-sectional study [11], which reported that most benzene-exposed individuals were young to middle-aged adults, as this demographic is more likely to be employed in manufacturing, petroleum, and industrial sectors where benzene exposure is common. Also a

descriptive analysis of chronic benzene poisoning cases in China, found that the average age of affected workers was approximately 43 years, with exposure spanning an average of about 11 years [7]. This similarity suggests that younger adult workers remain at elevated risk and underscores the importance of targeted preventive strategies. The age distribution thus highlights the importance of implementing occupational safety measures specifically aimed at protecting younger workers from long-term benzene exposure and its potential health consequences.

Workers had lower mean total cholesterol and HDL, while LDL and triglycerides were higher compared with non-exposed controls. Hematologically, petrol station workers showed slightly higher mean RBC, hemoglobin, and WBC counts [12,13]. Lipid profile and cardio metabolic signals. Several recent research and reviews have linked benzene and other gasoline-derived volatile organic compounds (VOCs) to poor cardiometabolic outcomes, such as dyslipidemia and increased cardiovascular risk. Long-term and low-level ambient benzene exposure has been related to increased cardiovascular mortality and cardiometabolic changes in population-based studies [13,14]. These findings support our observation of unfavorable lipid changes (higher LDL and triglycerides, lower HDL) among exposed workers [15].

The hematological alterations described in the literature are diverse. Several cross-sectional studies among petrol station and gasoline workers revealed changed blood indices—some detected decreases in red cell indices and hemoglobin consistent with the known myelotoxicity of benzene, while others reported increases in RBC and inflammatory markers (e.g., WBC, ESR) [12,16]. Our results (slightly higher RBC, Hgb, and WBC in workers) are consistent with recent petrol-station studies that reported increases in several blood parameters among exposed groups [17]. Possible reasons for variations Exposure and monitoring: Studies that found lower hematologic counts often had larger internal benzene doses (biomarkers) or longer cumulative exposures. If the Basrah workers in our study have sporadic or moderate exposures, this might explain the absence of blatant cytopenias and the presence of minor elevations in inflammatory cells.

Several participants reported chronic conditions (diabetes, hypertension, anemia) which can independently affect both lipid profiles and hematological parameters [14]. Smoking status, diet, physical activity, and medications were not fully adjusted for and could contribute to raised LDL and triglycerides or to shifts in WBC and hemoglobin. Impacts on public health Outcomes of dyslipidemia (greater LDL and triglycerides; lower HDL) and changed blood indices among gas station workers raise concerns about an elevated cardiovascular and hematologic risk in this occupational group. Our findings, combined with mounting evidence that long-term benzene exposure increases mortality and cardiometabolic risk, highlight the importance of preventive measures such as improved station ventilation, the use of personal protective equipment (PPE), routine medical surveillance (lipid profile and CBC), and biomonitoring of benzene metabolites whenever possible.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study discovered negative lipid changes and slight variations in hematological indices among fuel station

workers compared to controls. We recommend: periodic medical surveillance for petrol station workers, including CBC and lipid profile, the implementation of engineering controls and PPE to reduce inhalation exposure, and future studies with larger sample sizes, longitudinal design, and biomonitoring of benzene metabolites to clarify exposure-response relationships.

Ethical Approval

This study was conducted with the verbal consent of all participants and with the approval of the Institutional Ethics Committee at the Southern Technical University.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest in this article.

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